

Paper 8

NEED FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CHOICE BASED CREDIT SYSTEM (CBCS) IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The contribution by the Indian Scholars to the education is extraordinary. We have great history of renowned Universities like Nalanda University, Takshashila University, Kashi University offering the best of its value added education to the students. The Indian education system which was so called “GURUKULA” system transferring the knowledge to the needy students. In the course of time the aspirants who were called the disciples were living along with the teachers to learn both theoretical as well as practical knowledge from the teacher. But by the influence of Mechal education system the teaching learning methodology got changed its style. Teacher centric teaching learning environment came into existence. This system which is still followed does not give importance to learners to be active. They are just passive listeners. Looking into this scenario the MHRD department of central government is trying to introduce Choice Based Credit System in the higher education system. The main idea is to give the student an open choice to select the subjects of multiple disciplines for the study. This paper contains the idea about the CBCS system in Under Graduate program and the need, benefits of the same. This paper contains the various criteria introduced in CBCS system to make a Learner an active learner. The paper suggests a platform to facilitate a learner to acquire knowledge in multiple domains.

Keywords: CBCS, choice based, education, multiple discipline, domain, under graduate

1. Introduction:

India is a country which is famous for its rich heritage in education. Our country had its rich heritage of education system several thousands of years ago where there were no civilization in many of the foreign countries [1]. Our country had teaching learning environment in all sorts areas like political science, finance, law, civilization etc. Even our country had teaching and learning environment on medicine, surgery, aeronautics and much more. The teaching learning methodology was using Sanskrit as a

language and all the necessary information were clearly explained using slokas. This system of teaching learning was called GURUKULA system of teaching [2]. The learners had to make a lot of sacrifice to gain the knowledge. They had to live with the teachers for nearly 10 to 15 years to gain knowledge. The learning environment was suitable for teaching and learning only[3]. The gurukulas were located away from the general civilised area. The gurukula was located in forest where there was a peace of mind for teaching and learning, a room for concentration, a place for learning life style along with the study were available. The students were not having the time limit for the study. If a student was a quick learner he could finish his studies much earlier and help his teacher in teaching, thus getting more knowledge on the subject by means of teaching experience[4]. If a student was a slow learner then he could take more time to get the knowledge. The examination pattern was also different from the current examination. Students were not given the time table for examination well in advance. The examination was done along with their regular classes wherein the teacher could announce the examination then and there only. Finally his knowledge was tested in front of the learned scholars and teachers. There used to be no syllabus, no question paper etc. For the examination. The student had to face the questions asked by the panel of experts. The examination pattern used to take hours together to extract the knowledge about the subject. The questions would be some application oriented which was some way related to the subject. Totally the teaching and learning environment was dedicated to transformation of knowledge from teaching domain to the learning domain[5].

Indian gurukula system of education was looked after by the great emperors of those days. It was a prestige for the emperors to contribute more and more towards the gurukula based education system[6]. We had many great universities like Nalanda, Kashi, Takshshila etc which were considered to be the top most universities in the world. People for foreign country used to come to such universities for the study.

The political and social attack of foreign countries to India brought a major change in education system. The western countries who ruled India destroyed the Indian culture of education in order to publish their religion purposefully[7]. The introduction of classroom based education system is started where the teacher and a student used to meet for a couple of hours to exchange the knowledge. The student used to spend more of his time in other work than studying which is important for the student. The teaching and learning environment is diluted and distractions for the students as well as the teachers has become more and more. The impact of the classroom teaching thus became less concentration on studies, diluted teaching and learning process, pre planned examination where the students need only to answer the questions, a very narrow approach towards learning, less bonding between teacher and the student. There were many changes in the current classroom based teaching and learning methodology. However the concept of classroom based teaching has not changed [8].

Today we are having the credit based education system where the course will have a definite period of time of study like three years or four years etc [9]. Every course is now having semester scheme where in in a year the student is allowed to complete two semesters. As the year passes the student goes to higher semesters irrespective of the earlier semester papers. He will be allowed to go to the higher semesters even though he/she has backlogs earlier. He can get the degree only after passing in all the subjects of all

the semesters. He/she will be given double the time duration of the course to complete his/her papers and then only he/she will be eligible to get the degree. Otherwise he/she will be a loser.

The present teaching learning methodology does not give a student to select the subjects in the course. He/she is having a freedom only to select the course if eligible. But any subjects outside the course can not be learned by a student. For example a mechanical engineer will not be able to study any electronic subjects even though they are required in his/her career. An MBBS student is not able to study instrumentation engineering even though he/she will be requiring the knowledge to operate many medical equipment [10].

2. Objective:

The objective of this paper is to introduce a choice based credit system in higher education and to introduce the new teaching and learning methodologies to improve the quality of education in higher education system.

3. Methodology:

The methodology includes the preparation of course curriculum and the implementation of the new teaching methodology for the above said course curriculum.

First and foremost activity of any course is setting the course curriculum. The course curriculum must include the following points

- Learning objective of this course
- Pedagogy
- Duration of the course
- Total credit for the course
- Regulations
- Semester wise detailed subject with the reference books
- Examination pattern

The objective of the course must be clearly mentioned in the Course objective. The objective must include why the course is important?, What is benefit the student is going to get? What will be the course outcome? And the employability.

The pedagogy includes the techniques to be used in bringing up of the children and how best the course is offered to the students.

The duration must include the time limit of the course either 3 years-6 semester course or 4 years-8 semester course etc.

Duration of the course includes what is the duration for the course and how is it planned.

The total credit for the course is a tabular form of explanation of the subject wise, semester wise and total credit for the course.

The regulation for the course includes the eligibility criteria for getting admission to the course, attendance requirement for getting eligibility for the examination, promotion conditions and many other conditions for completing the course. The regulation must have all the solutions for the queries that may arise at any time.

The semester wise detailed syllabus contains all the details about topics to be covered and what are teachers going to teach on every topic and the corresponding reference books for the subject.

Examination pattern includes the regulation for conducting the examination, method of examination, paper valuation after examination, result announcement, Credit calculation Grade calculation with Semester Grade Point Average (SGPA) and Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) etc.

The new model contains the modified detailed syllabus. In this model the detailed syllabus contains three parts namely

- Hard core
- Soft core
- Inter disciplinary core

In the hard core the subjects are taken which are strongly connected with the course. These are compulsory subjects to be learnt.

In the soft core the subjects are related to the course itself. But there will be many topics related to the course out of which the student need to select either one or two or three depending on the course structure. These two discipline are related to the course only.

In case of Inter disciplinary core the student has to learn from a different domain where in the subjects are no way connected to the course.

The idea here is the teaching environment is providing a lot of opportunities for the learner to select his/her interested subjects. This gives raise to a multidimensional knowledge for the student which is more helpful in ones career.

The new model of teaching does not entertain a student getting failed in any subject. The teaching domain is always teaching all the papers in both even and odd semesters. Students are free to attend the classes of their choice. The examination system puts condition for attendance, assignments, internal examination and minimum cutoff for the external examination performance. Students can take any

number of classes more than the minimum classes and appear before the examination. If by anyway the student fails in that subject he/she can re attend the class of the failed subject until he/she passes in the examination.

4. ABCD Analysis:

4.1 Advantages

- The new model is purely student friendly wherein he/she can take his/her own time to clear the paper subject to maximum attempt time period.
- The student will not be having a concept of fail in any paper
- The student will not be under pressure to complete the paper in the semester end examination.
- The student will get an opportunity to re attend the classes of the failure subjects.

4.2 Benefits:

- Students are free to select the soft core papers and interdisciplinary subjects.
- Students get knowledge in multidisciplinary subjects.
- This model is student oriented

4.3 Constraints:

- The teachers need to acquire more and more knowledge in the subject they teach.
- A perfect co ordination is required when interdisciplinary subjects are considered.
- More number of teachers required as all the subjects are being taught during both odd and even semesters.

4.4 Drawbacks:

The new model is not that easy to adopt as it is a team work of all sorts of people from different domain. The credit system, course pattern and examination system must be unique. It is difficult to bring this awareness among the teachers and learners. This model may take several years to implement because this concept must be understood by All.

5 Conclusion:

The new model is creating a dramatic change in the current education system. Here the system is student centric rather than teacher centric. The student is free to select the subjects of his choice and has a freedom to pass in the corresponding subject. This gives rise to the stress free learning environment for the student. But achieving this is not so easy. It requires enough man power which is a burden for the management, class rooms for teaching all the subjects, uncertainty in number of students for a paper,

coordination among the different stream of subject and courses in order to manage interdisciplinary subjects and lac of the knowledge in the above concept.

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